

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF GREEN ENERGY IN THE ECONOMY

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"The future of human civilization will be green or not at all" The number of projects in the field of renewable energy sources is gradually increasing in our country, and none of them involves the provision of state guarantees. This, in turn, creates an opportunity for the creation of public-private partnerships in the field. The offers made by investors clearly show that the interest of major energy market participants to work in our country is increasing, and a favorable investment environment is being created for this.

97 percent of the energy production from renewable sources corresponds to the share of solar energy. Until 2050. Although the energy capacity of Uzbekistan's gross domestic product has been decreasing in recent years, this indicator remains much higher than that of developed countries. The average global energy capacity of GDP is currently 240 kilograms of oil equivalent of 1,000 US dollars. However, the energy capacity of Uzbekistan's GDP is almost four times higher than that of the European Union and twice the world average.

Renewable Energy Potential In 2018, Uzbekistan ratified the Paris Agreement and accepted a national commitment to reduce direct emissions per unit of GDP by 10% by 2030 compared to 2010. In 2019-2030, Uzbekistan aims to increase the share of RES in the total production of electricity to more than 25 percent by 2030.

It also plans to double the energy efficiency index, reduce the carbon intensity of the gross domestic product, and provide for the entire population and everyone. economic sectors with access to modern, cheap and reliable energy.

Uzbekistan's large RES potential can stimulate the significant development of a green, ecologically clean economy.

In fact, the technical potential of solar energy is almost four times more than the main energy consumption of the country. Its favorable climate and geographical location allowed Uzbekistan to use solar energy for various industrial purposes. The wind energy potential is 2.2 Mtoe, with 19% technical development possible. It is expected to increase the power generation capacity by 2.5 times and double the annual production by 2030.

Today, many countries' renewable energy goals include reducing greenhouse gas emissions, increasing the share of renewable energy in final energy consumption, and meeting energy demand. Development of renewable energy in Uzbekistan and increasing its share in the total energy balance are also being developed. In particular, this will increase the share of renewable energy in total electricity production from 10-12 percent in 2018 to 20 percent by 2025, including the share of hydroelectric power plants from 10-12 percent to 15.8 percent, and solar energy from 1.95 percent to 2.3 percent. and wind power from 1.36% to 1.6%.

Factors hindering the development of renewable energy sources, as in other developing countries, a number of factors hinder the development of renewable energy sources in Uzbekistan.

First, the high cost of renewable energy production and its limited production capacity compared to traditional energy sources, as well as the low cost of traditional energy sources compared to other countries. The cost of producing electricity from RES in developing countries is still high, and Uzbekistan provides its population with cheap electricity. leads the group of supplying countries: in Uzbekistan in 2022, the average price of 1kWh of electricity was 0.024 US dollars, while in Kazakhstan this figure was US dollars. 0.035; 0.07 USD in Turkmenistan; 0.048 USD in Russia; 0.13 USD in China. For comparison, the cost in developed countries: 0.338 US dollars in Germany; \$0.186 in the UK; \$0.333 in Denmark;

and USD 0.318 in Belgium.

Secondly, there are no special financial support mechanisms (tariffs and taxes) that encourage the use of RES. The legal basis for the economic mechanisms of promoting the use of RES is insufficient.

Thirdly, progressive techniques and technologies based on modern control systems are not sufficiently developed. One of the main reasons for the low rate of RES development is the technical imperfection of energy production technologies. In addition, the profitability of the short-term energy system is low.

Fourth, as in many other developing countries, public awareness of modern forms of energy, especially renewable energy, is low.

Fifth, innovative technologies of renewable energy sources are developing too fast to reach Uzbekistan. For example, solar panels made of semiconductor silicon were quickly replaced by photovoltaic panels made of amorphous silicon, and then by flexible solar cells. Due to the lack of indigenous technologies from renewable energy sources in Uzbekistan, the costs of purchase, installation and maintenance remain high. The rapid development of the industry requires the rapid replacement of outdated technologies with new ones.

Sixth, nuclear power affects the scale of renewable energy use and hinders the development of the energy sector. Research shows that producing clean energy from RES is 20 times more expensive than NPP. According to estimates, the world reserves of coal will last for 270 years, oil for 50 years and gas for 70 years, and uranium reserves used in nuclear power plants are 5,718,400 tons, which will last for 2,500 years. In 12 countries, the share of NPPs in electricity production is high and exceeds 30% (75% in France; 54% in Slovakia; 51% in Belgium and 46% in Ukraine).

An important tool for promoting renewable energy is the green certification system, which identifies and validates information on the composition and types of fuel used in the country and provides transparency on the origin of electricity. These certificates are also used for product branding.

Green certificates are used to encourage the use of renewable energy sources, as they are the basis for the government to provide subsidies, incentives and other types of financial support to renewable energy producers, consumers and suppliers.

Based on the above, we can say that traditional energy resources are non-renewable and limited, and are also responsible for climate change. Therefore, the energy needs of the growing population of Uzbekistan can be met only through green energy. But green energy technology and its products are very expensive, so people are less interested in them. They can be made accessible to all by investing in technology. With the right combination of geographic diversity and technological prowess, Uzbekistan can increase its green energy potential, thereby reducing its dependence on fossil fuel energy and handing over a greener Uzbekistan to future generations.

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